

Modified Resnet-50 Architecture for Scoliosis Detection

Ronnel C. Mesia, Dr. John Lenon E. Agatep

¹College of Communication and Information Technology President Ramon Magsaysay State University Zambales, Philippines

²Graduate School President Ramon Magsaysay State University Zambales, Philippines

Abstract- — Scoliosis is a condition where the spine curves abnormally, which can cause discomfort, pain, and difficulties with movement. It is essential to detect and diagnose scoliosis as early as possible to prevent further complications and improve treatment outcomes (Brackett, 2023). The main goal of this study was to improve classification accuracy of ResNet-50 architecture in detecting scoliosis on unclothed human back images, enabling early detection and intervention to prevent the progress of the spine curvature. The modified ResNet-50 architecture in this study incorporates global average pooling and reduces the size of the fully connected layers in the original ResNet-50 architecture. The data used in this study consists of images of normal and with scoliosis unclothed human back images. The dataset was sourced from public repositories, private individuals and patients at President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital Iba, Zambales. These images were annotated and validated by medical experts from PRMMH. The Modified ResNet-50 model showed outstanding performance with slight fluctuation in validation loss similar to the findings in the study of Artates et. al (2024) that despite of minimal validation loss fluctuations the model can still be more robust and reliable. The Modified ResNet-50 model achieved impressive results and outperformed the baseline ResNet-50 across multiple evaluation metrics. The Modified ResNet-50 model reached an accuracy of ninety-seven percent (97%), both precision and recall values of ninety-six-point five percent (96.5), and F1-Score, Macro & Weighted Average of ninety-seven percent (97%). These results indicate that the model is highly effective in accurately classifying unclothed human back images.

Keywords: Waste Management, Artificial Intelligence, Smart Cities, Deep Learning, Image Classification, Real- Time Tracking, Recycling, Upcycling, Cloud Computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The spine, or vertebral column, plays a crucial role in our daily lives, providing both structural support and flexibility. Scoliosis is a condition where the spine curves abnormally, which can cause discomfort, pain, and difficulties with movement. It is essential to detect and diagnose scoliosis as early as possible to prevent further complications and improve treatment outcomes (Brackett, 2023). Individuals with spinal conditions like scoliosis and ankylosing spondylitis often encounter obstacles when seeking employment and advancing their careers. These challenges can arise from inaccessible buildings and unconscious bias (APM, 2024). In the Philippines, former President Rodrigo R. Duterte has declared the month of June every year as “Scoliosis Awareness Month” to raise awareness on the disorder and promote its early detection (Parrocha, 2018). Moreover, Bonife-Kiamko founder of Scoliosis Philippines said in her interview with SunStar PH that there are three (3) million Filipinos diagnosed with scoliosis and need urgent medical treatment. The Scoliosis Philippines is actively pushing for a massive screening since there has been no massive screening in the country (Llemit, 2019). Traditional methods of diagnosing

scoliosis, such as X-rays and physical examinations, although effective, come with limitations including exposure to radiation and subjective interpretation (Mayo Clinic, 2023). These challenges highlight the need for innovative, non-invasive, and reliable diagnostic tools.

The advances in medical imaging and artificial intelligence (AI) have opened up new possibilities in healthcare. The integration of these two fields has transformed numerous aspects of medical practice, including early disease detection and precise diagnosis to personalized treatment planning and enhanced patient outcomes (Pinto-Coelho, 2023).

Lately, a significant advancement in machine learning technology, known as deep learning neural networks, has emerged. One of the most popular neural network architectures is the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) these networks excel at recognizing images, particularly those containing objects in it. In recent years, residual neural networks (ResNet) and their optimization have become focal points in deep learning research and are extensively utilized in medical imaging. Significant advancements have been made

in clinical diagnosis, staging, metastatic evaluation, therapy planning, and target selection for serious conditions such as tumors, cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases, and nervous system disorders. ResNet is advantageous for processing medical images because it can extract and classify complex features, thereby improving accuracy and strength. Its depth and precision make ResNet highly effective for a wide range of medical image processing tasks (Xu, Fu, & Zhu, 2023). As stated by Shrestha et al. (2021) in their study the current treatment in diagnosing scoliosis relies on manual spinal assessment, which has several limitations such as being tedious, time-consuming, and costly.

To address some of these limitations and enable early-stage predictive analysis for scoliosis detection, this research proposes a scoliosis detection model by modifying the ResNet-50 architecture. The main goal was to improve classification accuracy by utilizing transfer learning, the model aimed to categorize back images into two distinct classes. To measure its performance, the modified ResNet-50 model underwent rigorous testing and was compared against the unmodified ResNet-50 model. The experiments and analysis were carried out using the Google Colab platform.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

With a prevalence of 0.47% to 5.2%, adolescent idiopathic scoliosis (AIS) is the most prevalent kind of scoliosis in children over ten, according to Ramos et al. (2020). Without screening programs, AIS frequently stays undiagnosed in many nations until abnormalities develop and surgery is necessary. In order to promote the implementation of a school-based scoliosis screening program, this study evaluates the risk of AIS among sixth graders at a private school in the northern Philippines. In addition to unstructured interviews, screening techniques included the Adam's forward bending test, the leg length discrepancy test, and the posture deviation test.

According to the findings, kids under 50 kg had asymmetrical shoulders, most likely as a result of lugging bulky school bags for five to ten minutes per day. These elements point to a possible AIS risk. Implementing school screening programs as part of primary healthcare services could help prevent future deformities and the need for surgery. Given the complexity and subjectivity of traditional diagnostic techniques, Susa et al. (2022) emphasize the significance of effective and trustworthy medical image analysis in today's healthcare. They suggested an end-to-end pipeline that uses convolutional neural networks to evaluate the Cobb angle automatically and determine the severity of scoliosis. Based on Dice and Jaccard

similarity coefficients, the Residual U-Net architecture segmented vertebrae with an average accuracy of 92.95%. There was no significant difference between the machine-driven approach and physician measurements, as evidenced by a mean deviation of 1.57 degrees and a T-test p-value of 0.9028.

These results point to the possibility of using AI-assisted scoliosis assessment to make a quicker and more accurate diagnosis. Similarly, Maaliw (2023) highlighted the importance of prompt and trustworthy medical evaluations. In order to solve this, the researchers created SCOLIONET, an architecture for precise Cobb angle measuring based on convolutional neural networks. By using atrous spatial pyramid pooling for improved picture segmentation, the model was able to achieve high segmentation accuracy, as seen by its 97.50% Sorensen–Dice coefficient and 96.30% Intersection over Union. There was no discernible difference between the average deviation of 2.86 degrees and the t-test p-value of 0.1713 when compared to manual physician evaluations. These findings imply that SCOLIONET can facilitate quicker, more reliable scoliosis evaluations, enhancing the standard of patient treatment.

In 2020, Vergari et al. developed a CNN-based classification algorithm to automatically detect scoliosis treatments in radiographs, such as braces or spinal implants. Their model, combining CNN with discriminant analysis, achieved a high accuracy rate of 98.3% in classifying radiographs into treatment categories. This work highlights the potential of CNNs in automating the labeling of radiographs, which could streamline the use of large medical image databases and potentially extend to other classification tasks in radiography. Shrestha et al. (2021) focused on early-stage scoliosis detection using machine learning algorithms like Linear Regression and Support Vector Machines. Their point-based automated method aimed at analyzing spine X-ray images to detect scoliosis efficiently and accurately. This research emphasizes the importance of early detection in scoliosis management and the potential of machine learning to enhance diagnostic processes.

Moreover, Fraiwan et al. (2022) applied deep transfer learning to detect scoliosis and spondylolisthesis from X-ray images, achieving high accuracy in classification tasks. Their study underscores the robustness of deep learning models in diagnosing vertebral column disorders, providing a supporting tool for early and accurate medical intervention.

In search of a way to enhance measurement accuracy, Tan et al. (2018) designed an automatic scoliosis diagnosis and

measurement system using a U-net segmentation network. Their system accurately identified vertebral endplates and measured Cobb angles, demonstrating similarities to manual measurements. This research highlights the potential of deep learning to assist doctors in clinical diagnosis by improving measurement accuracy and consistency.

In 2020, Alharbi et al. proposed an automatic measurement algorithm for Cobb angles using deep CNNs, which processes X-ray images to detect vertebrae and measure angles using trigonometry. Their method showed high accuracy in estimating Cobb angles, indicating its potential clinical utility in automating scoliosis assessments and reducing the manual effort required. A fully-automated pipeline using deep learning for scoliosis analysis is developed by Imran et al. (2020), capable of identifying vertebrae and estimating Cobb angles from spinal X-ray images. Their system promises to enhance the reliability and efficiency of scoliosis assessments, reducing the reliance on manual analysis and potentially minimizing observer variation.

More so, Zhang et al. (2021) developed an advanced scoliosis detection by using a neural network, SpineHRNet, to predict coronal spine alignment from smartphone-acquired radiograph images. Their approach focused on predicting vertebral landmarks and computing Cobb angles, demonstrating significant correlations with ground truth measurements. This study underscores the viability of using deep learning for accurate scoliosis assessment even with suboptimal image quality, thereby supporting telemedicine applications.

In the study conducted by Kokabu et al. (2021) evaluated a deep learning algorithm using three-dimensional depth sensor imaging for predicting Cobb angles in adolescent idiopathic scoliosis (AIS). Their study achieved a strong correlation between actual and predicted Cobb angles, demonstrating the algorithm's accuracy and reliability. This approach highlights the advantages of integrating advanced imaging techniques with deep learning for precise scoliosis assessment.

Similar to the previous studies, Wahyu et al. (2022) developed AutoSpine-Net, a deep learning architecture for detecting spine vertebrae and classifying Cobb angles in AIS. Their system achieved high accuracy in assessing scoliosis severity and offers a tool for augmenting Cobb angle measurements in clinical settings, potentially reducing observer variability.

In the exploration by Ha et al. (2022) in comparing AI-generated scoliosis measurements with clinical reports, using a Faster R-CNN Resnet-101 model for vertebral segmentation and Cobb angle estimation. Their findings showed significant

correlation between AI and human measurements, supporting the feasibility of AI systems in automating scoliosis diagnosis and improving consistency in clinical assessments.

The study conducted by Ali et al. (2019) tackles the challenge of early detection in breast cancer, a leading cause of female cancer deaths globally due to its asymptomatic early stages. It explores nonlinear multimodal imaging as a promising technology to detect molecular changes and augment the sensitivity of existing screening methods. The study utilizes ResNet-50, a deep learning model, in two classification strategies: as a feature extractor and through fine-tuning. Evaluation methods include leave-one-patient-out cross-validation (LOPO-CV) and traditional training-test validation. The most effective approach involves fine-tuning ResNet-50 with LOPO-CV, achieving an 86.23% mean sensitivity in detecting breast cancer, underscoring its potential to enhance screening accuracy and facilitate early diagnosis.

Similarly, on the study conducted by Yuan et al. (2020) focuses on the threat of parotid gland tumors, a leading cause of facial paralysis, and underscores the importance of rapid imaging-based diagnosis. Utilizing a dataset comprising 51 CT images of malignant parotid tumors and 101 images of pleomorphic adenomas, the researchers developed an efficient machine learning algorithm for image classification. They chose the ResNet-50 deep learning model for its strong adaptability and simplicity, eliminating the need for manual feature engineering. This research marks the first application of the ResNet-50 model for classifying parotid tumor CT images, achieving a 90% accuracy rate after 1000 iterations. The study also investigates the use of desensitization strategies to protect patient privacy, enhancing model performance and demonstrating significant potential for applications in medical big data.

The study conducted by Sarwo et al. (2019) explores the importance of automated logo and brand name detection in educational settings, highlighting the necessity for models that can achieve both high speed and accuracy. It discusses the challenges of the one-stage detector framework, which, despite being innovative, requires significant computational power and time for training and detection. The study introduces new variants of ResNet models based on ResNet-50 to improve performance. The results showed that the proposed Model 2 attained an average precision (mAP) of 0.408 with a training duration of 1.41 hours, while the original ResNet-50 achieved a higher mAP of 0.556 but required 1.91 hours of training. In terms of detection speed, Model 2 operated at 23.47 frames per second (fps), compared to the original ResNet-50's 29.33 fps.

The investigation carried out by Li (2020) examines deep learning network models for static gesture recognition. Focusing on the ResNet-50 model, the study develops a gesture control system for web browsers. This system uses a gesture matching controller with Selenium, a tool for web application testing, to manage browser functions. Eight control gestures were defined to execute tasks like opening the Firefox browser, accessing Baidu news, maximizing and restoring the window, navigating pages, and closing the browser. Tests showed that the system effectively recognized and performed these gestures, demonstrating the method's feasibility.

In the same way, Tian et al. (2019) examines the performance of various convolutional neural networks, including VGG16, VGG19, Inception, Xception, and ResNet-50, in identifying modulation patterns of constellations. The experiments reveal that ResNet-50 excels in this task. Using ResNet-50, the study also identifies both the modulation mode and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the constellations. With an SNR accuracy requirement of 1 dB, the recognition rate is 60%, and with an SNR accuracy of 2 dB, the recognition rate increases to 85%. The research performed by Chu et al. (2020) tackles the complex task of generating descriptive captions for images automatically.

Their proposed model, AICRL, combines ResNet-50 for image encoding and LSTM with a soft attention mechanism for decoding. ResNet-50 serves as the encoder, using a convolutional neural network to create a detailed representation of the image by embedding it into a fixed-length vector. The decoder, powered by LSTM and incorporating soft attention, focuses selectively on parts of the image to predict subsequent sentences in the caption. Trained on the MS COCO 2014 dataset, AICRL maximizes the likelihood of generating accurate description sentences for training images and undergoes evaluation using metrics like BLEU, METEOR, and CIDEr. Experimental findings affirm AICRL's effectiveness in generating meaningful image captions automatically.

According to Wu et al. (2019) the accurate economic indicators are crucial for policymakers and researchers in assessing poverty levels regionally. The study introduces a novel method that combines remote sensing imagery and machine learning for estimating these indicators. Using ResNet-50, a deep residual neural network, the research trains on nighttime light intensity from satellite images to extract meaningful features. These features are then utilized in ridge regression to predict economic metrics like gross domestic product (GDP) and total retail sales of consumer goods

(TRSCG). Evaluation through Pearson coefficients shows strong correlations of 0.85 for both GDP and TRSCG, outperforming traditional linear regression models. This underscores the method's effectiveness in predicting economic indicators, with the added benefit of using publicly accessible satellite data, making it easily adaptable for application in various regions.

The research undertaken by Yan et al. (2020) introduces the use of ResNet-50 to classify surface features on Mars, specifically craters and lineament structures such as dorsum and vallis. They developed a dataset with 300 samples per category, divided into a training set and test set in a 4:1 ratio. After optimizing the network structure and parameters, the model achieves accuracies of approximately 85% for crater classification, 92% for dorsum, and 80% for vallis. This demonstrates ResNet-50's effectiveness in accurately distinguishing between different geological features on the Martian surface, showcasing its potential for planetary exploration and scientific research.

As stated in the study by Mukti et al. (2019) identifying plant diseases poses a significant threat to food safety in agriculture. Using advanced Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), particularly ResNet-50, the research explores the cost-effective approach of transfer learning to develop a precise model for classifying 38 different types of plant leaf images. The dataset includes 70,295 training images and 17,572 validation images. The study compares ResNet-50 with other popular pre-trained models such as VGG16, VGG19, and AlexNet. Results indicate that the ResNet-50-based model achieves exceptional training accuracy of 99.80%, demonstrating its effectiveness in accurate plant disease detection through transfer learning methods.

Similarly, Theckedath et al. (2020) explores the development of intelligent human-computer interface systems through the detection of seven fundamental affective states: Angry, Contempt, Disgust, Fear, Happy, and Sad. Previous systems required full, unobstructed face images, but this study employs convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with transfer learning. It compares three pretrained networks: VGG16, ResNet-50, and SE-ResNet-50, which includes a squeeze and excitation architectural block within ResNet-50. After training these modified networks on a dataset of affective images, the study achieves validation accuracies of 96.8% for VGG16, 99.47% for ResNet-50, and 97.34% for SE-ResNet-50. Evaluation metrics such as precision and recall affirm that all three networks effectively detect affect states, with ResNet-50 demonstrating the highest accuracy.

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Proposed Modified ResNet-50 architecture

1. Modified ResNet-50 Architecture

The modified ResNet-50 architecture addresses the challenge of having a less accuracy commonly found in using a pre-trained CNN model. A recent study by Zhang et al. (2023) states that employing a pre-trained ResNet-50 model does not assure optimal performance in classifying images. To address this, the researcher replace the top layer with a dense layer with a dimension of 128 avoid overfitting. These dense layers enable the modified ResNet-50 model to adapt its learned features without overfitting and more precisely to the specific requirements of the back image classification. Thus, enhancing the model's ability to learn and generalize from the data can potentially improve performance metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, Macro average, and weighted average, depending on the application and the quality of the data.

2. Dataset

Table I: Original Dataset Partition

Class (Human Back Images)	Training (70%)	Validation (15%)	Testing (15%)	
Normal	145	32	32	209
Scoliosis	145	32	32	209
			Total	418

The dataset undergoes division into three segments: seventy percent (70%) for the training set, fifteen percent (15%) for the validation set, and fifteen percent (15%) for the testing set. The training set facilitates the refinement of the modified ResNet model, while the validation set gauges its performance. Subsequently, the testing set is utilized to evaluate the accuracy of the trained modified ResNet model. Additionally, data augmentation is used to create instances of unclothed human back images to increase the number of

images in the dataset. According to Krizhevsky, Sutskever & Hinton, 2012; Zoph et al., 2019 as cited by Shahinfar et. al (2020), Data augmentation was used to improve model resilience by including random changes in training data. It involved applying stochastic changes to images and utilizing both original and enhanced data in training. This method increases test accuracy and model performance. The following seven methods were applied: symmetric wrapping, rotation, zooming, random cropping, horizontal flipping, and brightness and contrast modifications. Data augmentation was also used on the test dataset (Howard, 2018 as cited by Shahinfar et. al (2020)). By combining seven augmentation techniques with the original dataset, this process expanded the size of the dataset by eightfold.

Table II: Augmented Dataset Partition

Class (Human Back Images)	Training (70%)	Validation (15%)	Testing (15%)	
Normal	1,160	256	256	1,672
Scoliosis	1,160	256	256	1,672

To improve model generalization, data augmentation was applied to each image, including symmetric wrapping, rotation, zooming, random cropping, horizontal flipping, brightness and contrast modifications. This augmentation process expanded the dataset size as shown in table 2 by eightfold that produced a total of 3,344 photos. All images were in RGB and resized to 224×224 pixels.

3. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the performance of the standard and modified ResNet model, several efficiency metrics are considered, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, macro average, and weighted average.

- **Accuracy:** It is used to a measure of a model's performance, representing the proportion of true results (both true positives and true negatives) among the total number of cases examined.
- **Precision:** It is used to measure the ratio of true positive results to the total predicted positive results, indicating the accuracy of the positive predictions made by the model.
- **Recall:** It is used to measure the ratio of true positive results to the total actual positives, indicating the ability of the model to find all relevant cases.

- **F1 Score:** It is used to measure the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a single metric that balances both concerns.
- **Macro Average:** It is used as an averaging method in classification metrics that calculates the metric independently for each class and then takes the average, treating all classes equally.
- **Weighted Average:** It is used as an averaging method in classification metrics that calculates the metric independently for each class and then takes the average, weighting each class by its proportion in the dataset.

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

The model was evaluated on a test set consisting of 256 images each class (15% of the total dataset)

Table III. Model Evaluation Results

Metrics	Unmodified ResNet-50	Modified ResNet-50
Accuracy	71%	97%
Precision	71.5%	96.5%
Recall	71%	96.5%
F1 Score	70.5%	97%
Macro Average	71.33%	97%
Weighted		

Figure 2: Training/Validation Accuracy and Loss of unmodified ResNet-50

Figure 3: Training/Validation Accuracy and Loss of modified ResNet-50

The performance comparison between the unmodified and modified ResNet-50 models demonstrates the significant improvement achieved through architectural modifications. The modified ResNet-50 model achieved an accuracy of 97%, according to the results. The modified ResNet-50 model obtained 97% accuracy, which is significantly higher than the unmodified model's 71% accuracy. Precision and recall values improved significantly, climbing from 71.5% and 71%, respectively, to 96.5% in the modified ResNet-50 model. These findings indicate that the modified network not only makes more accurate predictions, but also strikes a good balance between detecting scoliosis instances and preventing false positives.

The F1 score, which represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall, increased from 70.5% to 97%, showing the modified ResNet-50 model's superior classification performance. Furthermore, the macro average and weighted average metrics improved from 71.33% in the unmodified model to 97%, suggesting consistent excellent performance across both classes. These enhancements can be attributed to changes made to the model architecture, such as the addition of dropout layers and fine-tuning of the later convolutional blocks, which most likely increased feature extraction and reduced overfitting. Despite the positive results, certain limitations must be addressed. The dataset employed, although augmented, is small and may not fully represent the variety of unclothed human back images observed in real-world clinical settings. Future study should include analyzing the model on a larger and more diversified dataset, as well as in real-time clinical scenarios.

Overall, the results show that the updated ResNet-50 model is a highly accurate and reliable method for detecting scoliosis, with great potential for integration into diagnostic support systems. Future research may look into lightweight versions of the model that are appropriate for mobile health applications or community-based screening programs.

V. CONCLUSION

This work described a modified ResNet-50 model for classifying unclothed human back images into normal and with scoliosis categories. The suggested model outperformed the baseline ResNet-50, achieving 97% accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. These findings show that the model has the potential to be a reliable tool for detecting early scoliosis. Despite the positive results, the study was constrained by a small dataset size, which may affect generalizability. Future research should focus on validating the model using larger, more diverse datasets and investigating its integration into real-world screening systems or mobile health applications.

REFERENCES

1. Alharbi, R. H., Alshaye, M. B., Alkanhal, M. M., Najla Hamandi Alharbi, Alzahrani, M. A., & Alrehaili, O. A. (2020). Deep Learning Based Algorithm For Automatic Scoliosis Angle Measurement. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iccais48893.2020.9096753>
2. Ali, N., Quansah, E., Köhler, K., Meyer, T., Schmitt, M., Popp, J., Niendorf, A., & Bocklitz, T. (2019). Automatic label-free detection of breast cancer using nonlinear multimodal imaging and the convolutional neural network ResNet50. *Translational Biophotonics*, 1(1-2). <https://doi.org/10.1002/tbio.201900003>
3. APM AU (2024). Retrieved July 15, 2024, from <https://apm.net.au/job-seekers/resources/8-of-the-best-job-ideas-for-people-living-with-scoliosis>
4. Brackett, N. (2023, April 25). The Importance of Early Detection and Diagnosis of Scoliosis. Aventura Wellness & Rehab Center. <https://www.miami-chiropractors.com/the-importance-of-early-detection-and-diagnosis-of-scoliosis/>
5. Chu, Y., Yue, X., Yu, L., Sergei, M., & Wang, Z. (2020). Automatic Image Captioning Based on ResNet50 and LSTM with Soft Attention. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 2020, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8909458>
6. Fraiwan, M., Audat, Z., Fraiwan, L., & Manasreh, T. (2022). Using deep transfer learning to detect scoliosis and spondylolisthesis from x-ray images. *PLOS ONE*, 17(5), e0267851. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0267851>
7. Ha, A., H, B., Bartret, A. L., Fang, C., Hsiao, A., Lutz, M., Banerjee, I., Riley, G. M., Rubin, D. L., Stevens, K. J., Wang, E., Wang, S., Beaulieu, C. F., & Hurt, B. (2022). Automating Scoliosis Measurements in Radiographic Studies with Machine Learning: Comparing Artificial Intelligence and Clinical Reports. *Journal of Digital Imaging*, 35(3), 524–533. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10278-022-00595-x>
8. J. S. Artates, J. J. Martinez, R. P. Medina and V. O. Ecunar, "Coral Health Assessment Using Modified Inception V3 and DenseNet 121," 2024 15th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC), Jeju Island, Korea, Republic of, 2024, pp. 2082-2086, doi: 10.1109/ICTC62082.2024.10826787.
9. Kokabu, T., Kanai, S., Kawakami, N., Uno, K., Kotani, T., Suzuki, T., Tachi, H., Abe, Y., Iwasaki, N., & Sudo, H. (2021). An algorithm for using deep learning convolutional neural networks with three dimensional depth sensor imaging in scoliosis detection. *The Spine Journal*, 21(6), 980–987. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spinee.2021.01.022>
10. Li, Z. (2020). Practice of Gesture Recognition Based on Resnet50. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1574, 012154. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1574/1/012154>
11. Llemit, R. L. G. (2019, July 26). 720,000 scoliosis patients in Mindanao. SunStar Publishing Inc. <https://www.sunstar.com.ph/davao/local-news/720000-scoliosis-patients-in-mindanao>
12. Maaliw, R. R. (2023). SCOLIONET: An Automated Scoliosis Cobb Angle Quantification Using Enhanced X-ray Images and Deep Learning Models. *Journal of Imaging*, 9(12), 265. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging9120265>
13. Maaliw, R. R., Ann, J., Alon, A. S., Lagman, A. C., Ambat, S. C., Garcia, M. B., Piad, K. C., & Corazon, Ma. (2022). A Deep Learning Approach for Automatic Scoliosis Cobb Angle Identification. 2022 IEEE World AI IoT Congress (AIIoT). <https://doi.org/10.1109/aiiot54504.2022.9817290>
14. Mayo Clinic. (2023, May 13). Scoliosis - Diagnosis and treatment - Mayo Clinic. <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/scoliosis/diagnosis-treatment/drc-20350721>
15. Mukti, I. Z., & Biswas, D. (2019). Transfer Learning Based Plant Diseases Detection Using ResNet50. 2019 4th International Conference on Electrical Information and Communication Technology (EICT). <https://doi.org/10.1109/eict48899.2019.9068805>
16. None Sarwo, Yaya Heryadi, Edy Abdulrachman, & Widodo Budiharto. (2019). Logo detection and brand recognition with one-stage logo detection framework and simplified resnet50 backbone. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ait49014.2019.9144794>

17. P. Shrestha, A. Singh, R. Garg, I. Sarraf, T. R. Mahesh and G. Sindhu Madhuri, "Early Stage Detection of Scoliosis Using Machine Learning Algorithms," 2021 International Conference on Forensics, Analytics, Big Data, Security (FABS), Bengaluru, India, 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/FABS52071.2021.9702699.
18. Parrocha, A. (2018, November 12). Duterte declares June as "Scoliosis Awareness Month" [Review of Duterte declares June as "Scoliosis Awareness Month"]. Philippine News Agency, 1. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1053691>
19. Pinto-Coelho, L. (2023). How Artificial Intelligence Is Shaping Medical Imaging Technology: A Survey of Innovations and Applications. *Bioengineering*, 10(12), 1435. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bioengineering10121435>
20. Ramos, B. A., Sable, L. S., Santos, R. G., & Bulusan, F. (2020). Screening for Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliosis among Grade 6 Pupils of a Private School in Northern Philippines: A Basis for Scoliosis Prevention Program. 2(1), 66–78.
21. S. Shahinfar, S., Meek, P., & Falzon, G. (2020). "How many images do I need?" Understanding how sample size per class affects deep learning model performance metrics for balanced designs in autonomous wildlife monitoring. *Ecological Informatics*, 57, 101085. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2020.101085>
22. Shrestha, P., Singh, A., Garg, R., Sarraf, I., Mahesh, T. R., & G Sindhu Madhuri. (2021). Early Stage Detection of Scoliosis Using Machine Learning Algorithms. <https://doi.org/10.1109/fabs52071.2021.9702699>
23. Tan, Z., Yang, K., Sun, Y., Wu, B., Tao, H., Hu, Y., & Zhang, J. (2018). An Automatic Scoliosis Diagnosis and Measurement System Based on Deep Learning. <https://doi.org/10.1109/robio.2018.8665296>
24. Theckedath, D., & Sedamkar, R. R. (2020). Detecting Affect States Using VGG16, ResNet50 and SE-ResNet50 Networks. *SN Computer Science*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-020-0114-9>
25. Tian, X., & Chen, C. (2019, September 1). Modulation Pattern Recognition Based on Resnet50 Neural Network. *IEEE Xplore*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICSP48821.2019.8958555>
26. Vergari, C., Wafa Skalli, & Laurent Gajny. (2020). A convolutional neural network to detect scoliosis treatment in radiographs. 15(6), 1069–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11548-020-02173-4>
27. Wahyu Caesarendra, Wahyu Rahmani, Mathew, J., & Thien, A. (2022). AutoSpine-Net: Spine Detection Using Convolutional Neural Networks for Cobb Angle Classification in Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliosis. Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering, 547–556. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1804-9_41
28. Wu, P., & Tan, Y. (2019, November 1). Estimation of Economic Indicators using Residual Neural Network ResNet50. *IEEE Xplore*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDMW.2019.00039>
29. Xu, W., Fu, Y.-L., & Zhu, D. (2023). ResNet and its application to medical image processing: Research progress and challenges. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 240, 107660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2023.107660>
30. Yan, P., Su, Y., & Tian, X. (2020). Classification of Mars Lineament and Non-Lineament Structure Based on ResNet50. <https://doi.org/10.1109/aecca49918.2020.9213607>
31. Zhang, H., Huang, C., Wang, D., Li, K., Han, X., Chen, X., & Li, Z. (2023). LEVERAGING TRANSFER LEARNING WITH A MODIFIED RESNET-50 MODEL FOR ENHANCED SOLID WASTE CLASSIFICATION. *Global Scientific Journals*, 11(10), 195–202. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378235453_LEVERAGING_TRANSFER_LEARNING_WITH_A_MODIFIED_RESNET-50_MODEL_FOR_ENHANCED_SOLID_WASTE_CLASSIFICATION
32. Zhang, T., Li, Y., Pui, J., Dokos, S., & Wong, K.-Y. K. (2021). Learning-Based Coronal Spine Alignment Prediction Using Smartphone-Acquired Scoliosis Radiograph Images. *IEEE Access*, 9, 38287–38295. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2021.3061090>